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بلدية دبي
DUBAI MUNICIPALITY

ص. ب. ٦٧ - دبي

تلفون: ٢١١٤٣

برقياً: بلدية

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المرجع

Date 12th July, 1971
التاريخ

Mr. D. Phillips,
Regional Director,
British Council,
DUBAI.

Dear Mr. Phillips,

DUBAI MUSEUM.

Thank you for your letter of the 25th June giving some suggestions on the Museum. We think it is a very good idea to find a postgraduate or a research worker who will be prepared to come out to Dubai to work in the Museum for 6 months to a year. We would certainly need a person who is interested in Museum work and preferably one who has worked in a Museum for a short time possibly in the long vacation.

We would be prepared to find accommodation and would consider paying a small salary.

We will be very pleased if you can make enquiries about this while you are in the U.K.

Yours sincerely,

KHALID HAMZA
DIRECTOR
DUBAI MUNICIPALITY.